

“UCHINCHI RENESSANS POYDEVORINI QO‘YISHDA FILOLOGIK TADQIQOTLARNING NAZARIY VA AMALIY AHAMIYATI”

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FEATURES OF LEVEL-BASED TEACHING OF RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN A NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITY

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Аннотация: В данной статье авторы акцентируют внимание на особенностях внедрения уровневого обучения при преподавании русского языка как иностранного в вузе с неязыковой подготовкой. В статье рассматриваются требования к уровню владения студентами неязыковых вузов русским языком как иностранным в соответствии с Концепцией развития иноязычного образования Республики Казахстан. Дифференцированное обучение рассматривается авторами на примере изучения русского языка в неязыковом вузе. В статье определены этапы, образовательные цели и результаты обучающего процесса. Авторами предложены рекомендации для реализации уровневого обучения русскому языку, а также обозначены актуальные проблемы. Авторы обращаются к необходимости формирования социокультурной компетенции студентов казахских групп в процессе обучения русскому языку как иностранному на примере выполнения заданий самостоятельной работы.

Ключевые слова: русский язык, уровневое обучение, самостоятельная работа, социокультурная компетенция.

Abstract: In this article, the authors focus on the features of the introduction of multi-level education in teaching Russian as a foreign language at a university with non-linguistic training. The article examines the requirements for the level of proficiency of students of non-linguistic universities in Russian as a foreign language in accordance with the Concept of the development of foreign language education in the Republic of Kazakhstan. Differentiated learning is considered by the authors based on the example of studying the Russian language in a non-linguistic university. The article defines the stages, educational goals and results of the educational process. The authors have proposed recommendations for the implementation of multi-level teaching of the Russian language, as well as identified actual problems. The authors refer to the need to form the socio-cultural competence of students of Kazakh groups in the process of teaching Russian as a foreign language on the example of completing tasks of independent work.

Keywords: Russian language, multi-level education, independent work, socio-cultural competence.

Introduction. In the Republic of Kazakhstan, when switching to a credit system of education in universities and the phased implementation of the cultural project "Trinity of Languages", level-level language teaching is successfully practiced, in

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this case, Russian as a foreign language. The current state of humanitarian education and the prospects for its renewal pose the task of improving and developing the linguistic culture of our society, in solving which a special role belongs to the Russian language as an academic subject. The purpose of teaching the Russian language course in universities is to teach language and speech development of students, the formation of linguistic, communicative and linguistic competence. In our opinion, it is also important to form socio-cultural competence as an integral part of communicative competence when learning a non-native language [1].

Main part. When teaching the Russian language, individual characteristics of students should be taken into account: the level of preparation for the subject; the level of development of thinking; different levels of speech culture; the degree of interest of students in improving their own language culture and motivation for studying the subject.

The language training of students of non-linguistic universities is a unified system in terms of the implementation of professional orientation in it. Taking into account different levels of language training, the technologies used to teach the Russian language and speech culture should contribute to the process of adaptation of students to a new educational environment; the formation of professional and cognitive activity of students; strengthening professional orientation.

Level-based learning is training in which the emphasis is on the development of skills in four types of speech activity (listening, speaking, reading, writing). The use of a level-based approach in a non-linguistic university makes it possible to see tangible results in language teaching. The teacher is interested in a full-fledged, conscious, competent mastering of the language being studied by the student and the possibility of moving to the next level of training [2].

Before the start of the training sessions, students are invited to pre-undergo diagnostic testing on issues aimed at identifying the level of knowledge in Russian grammar, reading and listening. First-year students are interviewed on social, social, cultural, and personality-oriented topics. Based on the results of testing and interviews, study groups are formed at the following levels of language training: Elementary level (A1), Basic level (A2), Academic level (B1, B2), Advanced level (C). At the elementary level, a first-year student after diagnostic testing should be able to build a written text on the proposed topic in accordance with a communicatively set attitude and based on questions. The type of text presented: specially composed or adapted plot texts (based on lexical and grammatical material corresponding to the elementary level of up to 200 words) [3].

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The goals and objectives of this course are to provide initial language training for a person who is able to build communication in conversationally significant situations. At the elementary and basic levels, it is very important to teach students how to write dictation and exposition. They should be educational in nature and not very large in volume. At the basic level, students work with texts such as narration, message, as well as mixed-type texts, specially composed or adapted. The student should be able to construct a written monologue of a reproductive nature on the proposed topic based on the text he has read or listened to in accordance with the communicative attitude; listen to statements on well-known topics, understand texts on personal and professional topics, be able to conduct a conversation on everyday topics, describe his experiences, be able to create simple texts on well-known topics, etc. The subject matter of the texts should be relevant to the sphere of everyday communication and social culture, the number of unfamiliar words should not exceed 2% [4].

An academic-level student has the opportunity to get acquainted with typical communicative situations and evaluate them correctly by choosing the appropriate speech behavior strategy. The material for classes is selected so that students, while learning the Russian language, acquire reading, writing and understanding skills of sounding speech based on the simultaneous development of the basics of grammar (phonetics, morphology and syntax) and word usage during constant repetition with gradual complication of tasks.

The purpose of the advanced level is the student's ability, based on the text read or perceived by ear, to record the necessary information in an abbreviated form using compression at all levels: text, paragraph, sentence; make a plan, summaries (short, detailed). At this level, the improvement and activation of Russian oral and written speech of students in various fields of communication is carried out and universal skills necessary for a future specialist in his practical activities are formed. Future specialists learn by linguistic means to solve real communicative tasks, conduct business negotiations, correctly compose documents, extract the necessary information from texts, compose texts in a scientific and professional way. Also, the objectives of the course include the ability to build a written monologue with the necessary communicative processing, transfer the content of someone else's speech with varying degrees of accuracy and completeness with reference to the source of information. In the field of productive written speech, a student should be able to build his own speech work of the type of message, narrative, reasoning or mixed type, make a program plan, theses of his message and speech [3].

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Results and Discussion. In the classroom, students are offered tasks of different difficulty levels [5, 250]. For example, at the secondary level, students are required to be able to summarize new information, draw conclusions, and use their knowledge in new situations. Each task is a mini-project that needs to be completed in one lesson. Active discussion of the objectives, plan and means of completing the task is encouraged.

Thus, students of the B1 level in the first semester acquire socio-cultural competence in the process of completing tasks of independent work. Students' independent work is carried out within the framework of project activities. During the semester, students complete two projects (one project during each milestone control). So, the first project is called "Russian traditions and customs". Students are divided into small groups, each group draws up a work plan and distributes the work among themselves. As part of another project, "The Best Museums in the World", students perform virtual excursions to the Hermitage, the Tretyakov Gallery and other museums in Russia.

Conclusions. Thanks to the selection of a system of tasks that form socio-cultural competence, it is possible to lead each student to a single goal, while relying on his knowledge and abilities. When performing such types of work in all level groups, students learn information about the country of the studied language, history and culture of the people in a convenient and accessible format.

At the same time, the goals and objectives of the Russian language course at different levels will be different:

1. Elementary and basic levels: The main goal is to provide initial language training capable of providing communication in conversational situations. At this level, much attention is paid to mastering writing skills, such as writing dictation and expositions. Students should also learn how to make monologue statements on the proposed topics, perceive and understand texts on various topics, and conduct a conversation on everyday topics.

2. Advanced level: At this stage, students acquire the skills of compressing information at different levels (text, paragraph, sentence), making plans and summaries. Students' oral and written speech is being improved in various fields of communication, and universal skills necessary for a future specialist are being formed. In addition, students learn to construct written statements of various types, such as communication, narration, reasoning, as well as to be able to convey the content of someone else's speech with varying degrees of accuracy and completeness.

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3. Project activities: Students are offered assignments of various levels of complexity, which are often mini-projects. The purpose of such assignments is to develop students' ability to summarize information, draw conclusions and apply their knowledge in new situations. Projects can be devoted to various aspects of Russian culture and traditions, which contributes to the formation of socio-cultural competence.

Thus, the Russian language course at different levels is aimed at developing both language skills and the ability to apply them in real communicative and professional situations. It covers both the basics of language and reading, as well as more advanced aspects such as information analysis and compression, the development of writing and working with various genres of texts.

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